

A Facile and High Yield Route to Succinanic Esters

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Synthetic application of phosphorous reagents for effecting esterification of the carboxyl function is a very common method¹⁻⁴. However, these reagents have many limitations such as vigorous conditions of heating to high temperature and longer reaction times¹, hygroscopic nature and instability of the reagent at high temperature⁴. We were interested in the esterification of maleanilic^{5,6} and succinanic acids which we required as intermediate in a synthesis.

Results and Discussion

Succinanic acids (1a-e) underwent an exothermic reaction when treated with thionyl chloride and the reaction mixture when quenched in water gave the corresponding imides (2a-e).

However, succinanic acid (1a) when reacted with thionyl chloride gave the desired ester (3a; Tables 1 and 2). The insolubility of certain acids in alcohols did not hinder their esterification, as under the reaction conditions the complete dissolution of the acid indicated the completion of the reaction.

This esterification of succinanic acids is proposed to proceed through intermediate 5 via succinisoimide⁷ (4) as it has been already confirmed by us in case of maleanilic acids⁸. It appears that intermediate 5 in case of succinanic acids rearranges so readily to the normal esters as to preclude isolation of imidate ester (6)⁹⁻¹¹. The product obtained is always the normal ester whether the reaction mixture is worked up after 0.5 h or after even 10 min.

This method cuts down the reaction time from 12-24 h to a uniformly short period of 3 h in case

of maleanilic acid⁸ and to about 0.5 h in case of succinanic acids, involving neither refluxing nor specialised reagents and is emerging out as a mixing affair process successful with higher alcohols in addition to previously reported methyl succinimides only⁴, irrespective of the substitution in the aromatic ring.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SUCCINANILIC ESTERS (3)

Compd. no.	R	R'	m.p. (b.p.)** °C	Yield* (%)
3a	H	C ₂ H ₅	65	95
b	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	60	95
c	OCH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	64	92
d	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	80	94
e	NO ₂	C ₂ H ₅	82	93
f	H	n-C ₃ H ₇	62	97
g	CH ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	—	80
h	OCH ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	70	98
i	Cl	n-C ₃ H ₇	82	95
j	NO ₂	n-C ₃ H ₇	64	97
k	H	n-C ₄ H ₉	—	75
l	CH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	—	65
m	OCH ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	—	80
n	Cl	n-C ₄ H ₉	—	95
o	NO ₂	n-C ₄ H ₉	—	95

*Satisfactory microanalyses were obtained for C, H and N.
**B.p. in case of liquid esters 3g, k-o could not be determined as these decompose on heating.

Experimental

All the m.p., b.p. values are uncorrected and were determined in a concentrated sulphuric acid bath. IR spectra were recorded on a Specord-600 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CCl₄/CDCl₃) on a

TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ)* OF SUCCINANILIC ESTERS (3)

Compd. no.	NH	ArH	(CH ₂) ₂	R	R'			
					OCH ₃	CH ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃
3a	8.496(s)	7.266(m)	2.568(s)	—	4.121(q)	—	—	1.201(t)
b	7.775(s)	7.165(m)	2.598(s)	2.295(s)	4.072(q)	—	—	1.260(t)
c	7.850(s)	6.943(m)	2.598(s)	3.740(s)	4.062(q)	—	—	1.260(t)
d	8.018(s)	7.305(m)	2.666(s)	—	4.111(q)	—	—	1.279(t)
e	8.320(s)	7.549(m)	2.744(s)	—	4.141(q)	—	—	1.299(t)
f	8.389(s)	7.275(m)	2.578(s)	—	3.984(t)	1.543(m)	—	0.908(t)
g	8.770(s)	7.012(m)	2.559(s)	2.197(s)	3.945(t)	1.504(m)	—	0.869(t)
h	8.154(s)	6.895(m)	2.588(s)	3.701(s)	3.994(t)	1.563(m)	—	0.918(t)
i	8.000(s)	7.305(m)	2.666(s)	—	4.072(t)	1.533(m)	—	0.957(t)
j	8.643(s)	7.812(m)	2.744(s)	—	4.102(t)	1.621(m)	—	0.957(t)
k	8.200(s)	7.207(m)	2.607(s)	—	4.072(t)	3.555(m')	1.357(m')	1.025(t')
l	7.950(s)	7.178(m)	2.598(s)	2.305(s)	4.072(t)	3.564(m')	1.396(m')	1.035(t')
m	8.164(s)	6.875(m)	2.588(s)	3.711(s)	4.043(t)	3.550(m')	1.396(m')	1.006(t')
n	8.740(s)	7.314(m)	2.627(s)	—	4.082(t)	3.594(m')	1.436(m')	1.035(t')
o	9.229(s)	7.988(m)	2.388(s)	—	4.102(t)	3.613(m')	1.523(m')	1.035(t')

*CDCl₃ for 3d, e, i, j, n, o and rest CCl₄; m' = ill resolved multiplets. t' = distorted triplets. Ir spectra of all the esters displayed bands at ~3 300 (NH), ~1 730 (ester C=O) and ~1 670 and 1 625 cm⁻¹ (amide I and II).

Hitachi-1500 FT NMR spectrometer (60 MHz), downfield from internal TMS.

Succinanic acids (1a—e): To hot succinic anhydride (10 g, 0.1 mol) solution in toluene (100–200 ml) was added amine (1 mol equiv. in about 10 ml of toluene) with constant stirring and stirring continued for 20–30 min. The reaction mixture then cooled to room temperature (refluxing for about 30 min was required with *m*-nitroaniline) and the resulting solid was recrystallised from alcohol.

Succinanic ester (3a—o). General procedure: To a solution or suspension of succinanic acids (2 g) in dry absolute alcohol (20–25 ml), was added double-distilled thionyl chloride (25–35 drops) within 5 min with stirring and stirring was continued for another 25 min under moisture-free condition. The reaction mixture was then quenched into ice-water in instalments with constant stirring. The solid esters separated were filtered, washed (2–3 times) with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol.

The liquid esters were extracted with ether, ether extract washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution, 1% HCl and water, dried (anhydrous Na₂SO₄), filtered, than ether evaporated or distilled under reduced pressure leaving behind the liquid ester. The esters were purified by distillation under reduced pressure.

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